

Determinants of Food Inflation in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstracts

This study investigated the determinants of food inflation in Ondo state, Nigeria from 2017 to 2023. The research made use of monthly secondary data from Ondo state budget office from the first quarter of 2017 to the fourth quarter in 2023. The study deployed descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) for the study. The result revealed that factors responsible of food inflation in Ondo state, Nigeria revealed that the root cause for the rising food inflation in Ondo state, Nigeria is caused mainly by insecurity, then followed by price of Premium Motor Spirit (petrol), Internal Generated Revenue (IGR) and rainfall (climate change). In conclusion, the results from this study implies that both state and national securities personnel's need to form a synergy (joint security team) in order to tackle insecurity headlong, as this will ensure optimum local food production output which in turn will clash the skyrocketing food prices within the state. Furthermore, the state government should invest massively into mechanize farming (agriculture), hydroponics farming, as well as improved seedling that can withstand the adverse effect of climate change. Lastly, the state government should have support genuine farmers will improve seedlings and fertilizers at a subsidized rate. This work can serve as a comprehensive guide in tackling the crises of food inflation in Ondo state, Nigeria.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The issue of rising inflation is a general phenomenon in most economies today. In the case of Nigeria, the rate of food inflation has increased markedly over the past five decades (Alam & Alam, 2016; Nakorji et al., 2023). Nigeria has been facing a persistent rise in the general price level over

the past couple of years. In fact, in more recent years, especially during the COVID and post COVID era, it has skyrocketed in a very significant magnitude to the extent of headline, food and core food inflation witnessing the rate of 21.47 per cent, 24.13 per cent and 18.24 respectively, in November 2022(Alam & Alam, 2016; Nakorji et al., 2023). The last time it got this high was 17 years ago, when in August 2005 it reached 28.21 per cent(Alam & Alam, 2016; Nakorji et al., 2023). The food component of the consumer price index basket is the major driver of the headline food inflation in Nigeria. Varying studies have therefore attributed the rise in food inflation to both fiscal and monetary policies. Other important factors such as, agro climatic conditions, structural bottlenecks, interest rates, currency devaluation and exchange rate etc. have contributed to the uptick in food inflation (Ahmed et al., 2014; Nakorji et al., 2023).

Accordingly, the World Health Organization(2021), reported that food prices have surged to levels not seen since July 2011. As food and fuel prices have risen worldwide, vulnerable populations and countries with low incomes have been particularly affected. The control of an economy becomes the pivot element upon which performance of Nigeria government and the world at large are based. Governments of countries feel compelled to ensure, through appropriate policies that their economies are managed to achieve desirable macroeconomic objectives. These objectives include: price stability; economic growth; full employment; and balance of payments equilibrium. The achievement of stable prices and attainment of sustainable economic growth had been the central objectives of macroeconomic policies for most countries in the world today. Thus, due to the achievement of other macroeconomic policies such as full employment and balance of payment equilibrium are ascertained establishing price stability and economic growth(Nakorji et al., 2023).

According to Keji and Omolade (2024) in conforming to this view, said that one of the characteristics of the current food inflationary trend is its ability to challenge the remedies in most developing countries. It is in light of this that the study aims at a critical examination of the significance of food inflation on the Ondo state Civil Servant in Nigeria household occasioned by their respective savings and consumption pattern. Every economy either poor or rich in their growth and development to the process of modernization could not have reach thence without the experience or the impact of food inflation. food inflation has been a menace to the economies of the nation with the tendency to resist solution. It is one of the greatest challenges of fewer developing countries using Nigeria economy as a reference.

According to the World Bank (2022), any citizen of an economy living below one dollar (\$) per day is inverse to poverty which is said to have been as a result of high food inflation coupled with low saving and high consumption rate in such an economy. Most household savings and their level of consumption has been based on the rationale expectation of food inflation in some economy in which their level of living is below the standard rate set by the World Bank.

1.1 Statement of Problem

According to Oyejide (2017), food inflation has been moving unrelentingly upward in Nigeria because of years of neglect of the social infrastructure and general mismanagement of the economy, currently, food inflation is double-digit and the surplus naira in circulation, scarcity of foods and fuel are part of the problem. According to him, in some parts of Nigeria, prices of food went up to 35.6% in July and 36.1% in August last year (2006).

Most of the recent studies on determinants of food inflation in Nigeria were at the macroeconomic / national level that is, as an individual country such as (Charles et al., 2022; Emeru, 2020; Inim et al., 2020) and except (Nakorji et al., 2023) examined determinants of food inflation at the state-level. However, Ondo state was exempted in the study of (Nakorji et al., 2023) as well as monthly data was not used. Thus, examining the determinants of food inflation using monthly data in Ondo state will contribute to the body of knowledge that takes cognizance of the unique economic setting of Ondo state. The study will be the first of its kind to use secondary data sources to estimate the effect of food inflation on household savings in Ondo state, Nigeria that is, using Ondo civil servants residing in Akure, Ondo state capital as a case-study. To the best of the knowledge of the author, few or no studies have examined the determinants of food inflation on household saving at the state level within the period of the study.

2.0 Literature Review

This section presents the conceptual review, theoretical review and empirical review of relevant literatures related to determinants of food inflation in Ondo State, Nigeria.

2.1 Conceptual review

2.1.1 Determinants of food inflation

Kaur (2023), like many economic concepts, food inflation has been defined in different ways by different writers. Before going further, it is essential to highlight some features of food inflation:

Food inflation is an engulfing process. Though it may start with just one or some prices, it spreads through input-output relations between different industries (Baqae& Farhi, 2022). Food inflation is a state of rising prices and not of high prices as such (Mankiw, 2021).

There is no absolute rate of price increase which will be said to demarcate between food inflation and non-food inflation situation (Samuelson & Nordhaus, 2010). Since the food inflation process is a self-perpetuating cycle, it creates expectations for continued price increases expectation in turn leads to the emergence of a behaviour pattern in the market which provides a further finding of food inflation (Akerlof & Yellen, 1985).

Thus, food inflation is generally used to describe a situation of rapid, persistent, and unacceptable rises in general price level in an economy resulting in a general loss of purchasing power of currency.

Mamudu and Gayovwi (2019) sees food inflation as policy induced in that it arises primarily from interference in the normal operation of market forces (the rule of demand and supply), distortion in prices, overvalued exchange rates, and Government control measures.

According to Begg (2002), he defines food inflation as a rise in the average price of goods over time, also pure food inflation is the spectral case in which all prices of goods and factors of production are rising at the same time. Therefore, three approaches are used to measure food inflation in an economy: The deflator of Gross National Product (GNP) which implicitly measures food inflation, The Consumer Price Index (CPI), and the Wholesale Price Index (WPI). In Nigeria, the food inflation rate is measured with the CPI which is easily and currently available on a monthly quarterly, and annual basis.

Fontaine (2021), says food inflation does not occur in vague but as part of a country's historical, social, political, and institutional evolution. More so, standard analytical categories of demand-pull and cost-push food inflation do not seem particularly useful in the analysis of food inflation in a developing economy taking Nigeria as among the three world countries that are less developed. The limitation to these approaches is recognized by development economists seeking a thorough understanding of the sources of food inflation during the development process.

2.2 Theoretical framework on determinants of food inflation

This section presents the relevant theories that underpin the effect of food inflation on household savings.

2.2.1 Fisher's equation of exchange

Sun and Philips (2024) equation of Exchange was by an American economist Irving Fisher in 1896 - 1910. The equation is a mathematical expression of the quantity theory of money, and it says the total amount of money that changes hands in an economy equals the total money value of goods that change hands, or that nominal spending equals nominal income.

Furthermore, the monetarist emphasizes the role of money as the principal cause of food inflation. They employ the familiar identity of Fisher's equation of exchange:

$$MV=PQ$$

Where: M is the money supply

V is the velocity of money

P is the price level

Q is the level of real output

Assuming V and Q are constant; the price level (p) varies proportionately as the supply of money (M). With flexible wages, the economy was believed to operate at full employment level. The labor forces, the capital stock, and technology also changed slowly over time (Sun & Philips, 2024).

Consequently, the amount of money spent did not affect the real output so a doubling of the quantity of money would result simply in doubling the price level. Until prices had risen by this proportion, individuals and firms would have excess cash which they would spend leading to a rise in prices. So, food inflation proceeds at the same rate at which the money supply expands. Naturally, when money increases it creates more demand for growth, but the supply of goods cannot be increased due to full employment of resources. It leads to a price rise, but it is a continuous rise in the money supply that will lead to true food inflation in such an economy (Friedman, 1968).

On the occasion of this, Gardiner (2006) the structuralizing had the view that food inflation is necessary with growth. According to this view, as the economy develops, rigidities arise which lead to structural food inflation. In the initial phase, there are increases in non-agricultural income accompanied by the high growth rate of population that tends to increase demand for goods, the pressure of population growth and rising urban incomes would tend to rise through a chain of reaction mechanism; which are prices of agricultural goods, the general price level and wages.

As the demand for agricultural goods rises, their domestic supply is inelastic, and the prices of agricultural goods rise. The output of such goods does not rise even if the price rises, this is due to the land tenure system. Moreover, the prices of imported products are relatively higher than their domestic prices; this tends to raise the price level further within the economy (Gardiner, 2006).

When the prices of food products rise, wage earners press for an increase in wage rate to compensate for the fall in their real incomes. The effects of an increase in the wage rate such as the cost of living on prices can be illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 1.1: Fisher's equation of exchange

Figure 1.1 shows when the wage rate rises, the aggregate demand for goods increases from D_1 to D_2 . However, the aggregate supply falls due to an increase in the labor cost which results in the shifting of aggregate supply curve from S_1S to S_2S . Since the production of goods is inelastic due to

structural rigidities after a point, the supply curve is shown as vertical from point e_1 onwards (Taylor, 2013). The initial equilibrium is at e_1 where the curves D_1 and S_1 intersect at the output OY_1 and the price level is OP_1 , when supply falls due to increasing in labor cost, the supply curve shifts from S_1 to S_2 , and it intersects the demand curve D_2 at e_2 and production falls from OY_1 to OY_2 and the price level rises from OP_1 to OP_2 . After these another cause of food inflation by the structuralizing is the rate of export growth in a developing economy which is low and unstable and is inadequate to support the required growth rate of the economy (Taylor, 2013).

The sluggish growth rate of exports and foreign exchange constraints led to the adoption of the policy of industrialization based on import substitution. Such a policy necessitates the use of protective measures which in turn tend to raise the price of industrial products and income in the non-agricultural sectors, thereby leading to further rise in prices (Tangermann, 2011).

Moreover, these policies lead to a cost-push rise in prices because of the rises in the price of imported materials and equipment and protection measures. Akidi et al. (2024) policies of import substitution also tend to be food inflationary because of the relative inefficiency of the new industries during the learning period. The secular deterioration in the trade of primary products of developing countries further limits the growth of income from exports which often leads to the exchange rate devaluation and causes food inflation in the economy (Umar & Umar, 2022). Viewing the two approaches together is admittedly quite possible and indeed important to analyze food inflationary pressure in developing economies by examining the changes in the rate of monetary expansion as labeled by the monetary approach.

De Gregorio (2012) the expansionary changes in monetary rates are in line with the broad definition of food inflation because it entails the prices of commodities in the economy and how they fluctuate over a specific period. Following the argument of the structuralized school, given the existence of structural bottlenecks or constraints in an economy seeking to attain a high level of growth and development, food inflation is unavoidable in that economy. Food inflation is structural and is generated during the attempt to develop in the face of structural rigidities (Pourroy, 2016; Muhammad, 2023).

Meanwhile, not every writer accepts the structural phenomenon or the degree of its significance in the food inflationary process, for instance, the monetarist focuses on the orthodox excess demand approach to food inflation in the developing economies. Not surprisingly, food inflation in this aspect arises from deficit financing, the exchange operation of the Central Bank of such economy, and expansion credit policy coupled with the operation of inefficient state-run enterprises. In Nigeria Ekpeyong (2023) therefore, the diagnosis of her food inflationary period is accepted on the thesis of characteristics of structural and rigidities that led to the nature and causes of food inflation in Nigeria's economy among which are structural changes in the economy. Rapid urbanization without

industrialization, food demand, and supply, wages determination process including oil production and money supply (Henderson, 2003). Theorists show that food inflation is necessary in an economy, while some consider it as a bad phenomenon in an economy, therefore analyzing the effects of it on household savings and consumption will be viewed positively and negatively (Rutten, 2013).

2.3 Empirical Review of literatures on determinants of food inflation

Victor et al (2020) examined other determinants of food inflation in Nigeria using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) method on quarterly data from January 1999- December 2018. Findings show that poor infrastructural development, exchange rate, political instability, corruption, and double taxation significantly stimulate food inflation rather than just money supply. The results show a causal relationship between other determining factors and food inflation. The ARDL result shows a significant long-short run relationship.

Berhanu and Girma (2023) identifying the major sources of food inflation observed Consumer Price Index (CPI) and its components annually from 1970 to 2011. To identify the major sources of food inflation in Ethiopia, the study presented, a VAR, co-integration analysis and the VECM allied with the descriptive analysis. The result of the VECM showed, only budget deficit as percentage of GDP is positively determining food inflation of Ethiopia in the short run. In the short run the Broad Money Supply, Real GDP, the imported food inflation of international petroleum price and the nominal exchange rate has insignificant effect of the annual Ethiopia's price hike. In the long run, the Ethiopia's food inflation mainly driven by the Broad Money supply, the Real GDP, interest rate, the Nominal Exchange Rate, and the budget deficit with high significance level. The Broad Money Supply in the economy and the Banks and Financial institutions average lending rate has a positive long run effect on food inflation. While, the Rainfall, the deficit budget and the Nominal Exchange rate has a negative long run determination of the price level in Ethiopia (Teshome & Kibret, 2021).

Okeke et al (2022) examined the determinants of food inflation in Nigeria using annual time series data covering the period of 1981 to 2017. This period has been carefully selected as it captures the different eras of policy implementation in Nigeria such as the pre-SAP era, SAP era, and the post-SAP era; and is long enough to make an objective assessment of the determinants of food inflation in Nigeria. The study applied Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) methodology based on the outcome of the ADF unit root test which revealed that the variables are integrated of I (1) and I. The ARDL bounds test result provided evidence of a stronghold long-run relationship among the variables. This necessitated the estimation of ARDL short-run and long-run results. The short-run results of both models revealed that YGAP, M2, TGE, TIMP and UEMPR were significant determinants of food inflation in Nigeria whereas the long-run results indicated that TGE, TIMP and UEMPR were significant determinants of food inflation in Nigeria (Adewuyi & Olowookere, 2021). The impact of YGAP, M2, TGE and TIMP was positive in both long and short runs whereas YGAP,

TIMP, TGE and UEMPR impacted negatively on food inflation in both periods. The outcome of all the diagnostic tests supported the acceptability of the models' results. The study concludes that both demand–pull and cost–push factors are responsible for food inflation in Nigeria and also provide the social infrastructure that would encourage private investment (Ogunleye & Falade, 2020).

Recently, Nakorji et al. (2023a) investigated what causes pressures on the domestic price level in various states (32) of Nigeria. We obtained quarterly data on food inflation, premium motor spirit (PMS), internally generated revenue (IGR), rainfall, and insecurity, from 2017Q1 to 2021Q4. Findings indicated petrol prices and insecurity to have a significant impact of food inflation. Specifically, higher PMS prices and higher levels of insecurity would result in higher levels of food inflation. Also, rainfall increases food productivity and ultimately lowers food inflation in the long run. Meanwhile, for states that depend more on IGR, the impact of IGR on food inflation is positive.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Data source

This section presents the data source of the study. Data sources for the study were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria, Akure office, Ondo state, and Ondo state government in monthly figures from the Bureau of Statistics, rainfall data was sourced from Nigeria Meteorological Agency (NiMet), Insecurity data was sourced from Nigeria Security watch database and Amotekun and finally the monthly price of premium motor spirit was sourced from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS): Premium Motor Spirit (petrol) price watch.

Table 1: Data Source

S/N	Abbreviation	Full meaning of Abbreviation	Source(s)
1	FInf	Food Inflation in Ondo state (monthly)	Ondo state Budget office, Akure, Ondo state
2	IGR	Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) (monthly)	
3	Rfall	Rainfall (monthly)	Nigeria Meteorological Agency (NiMet)
4	Insec	Insecurity (monthly)	Nigeria Security watch database and Amotekun
5	PMS	Premium Motor Spirit (monthly)	National Bureau of Statistics (NBS): Premium Motor Spirit (petrol) price watch

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

3.2 Model specification for Determinants of food inflation in Ondo state, Nigeria

The model specification for the determinants of food inflation in Ondo state, Nigeria adopted the work of (Nakorji et al., 2023) as follows.

$$FINF = f(IGR, RFALL, INSEC, PMS)..... (1)$$

Where FINF is food inflation rate in Ondo state, IGR is Internally Generated Revenue, Rfall is the rainfall, Insec is the insecurity and PMS is Premium Motor Spirit. However, in a regression form the model is expressed thus;

$$INF = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \log IGR + \alpha_2 Rfall + \alpha_3 Insec + \alpha_4 PMS + \mu$$

Where α_1 to α_4 are parameter estimates for each of the food inflation indicators as stated in the model. μ is the error term for the model which capture the stochastic variable.

Apriori Expectation

α_1 to $\alpha_4 > 0$: Positive relationship is expected between all the indicators of determinants of food inflation

4.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 indicates that all variables used as endogenous variable for food inflation are positive. This reveals that on the average all the endogenous variables. For instance, FINF, INSEC, LIGR, and LPMS all show low variability and look stable, possibly suggesting controlled or slowly changing indicators and RFALL is the outlier here with much higher dispersion, suggesting there are significant fluctuations maybe seasonal patterns or regional disparities if this is rainfall or a related metric. Lastly, skewness is minimal in most variables except for RFALL.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for Factors Responsible of Food Inflation in Ondo State, Nigeria

	FINF	INSEC	LIGR	LPMS	RFALL
Mean	276.6104	-0.16795	21.39953	4.980455	147.5
Median	275.6621	-0.16795	21.34337	4.982784	90.95
Maximum	307.7274	-0.1611	23.03937	4.986821	473.9
Minimum	248.4834	-0.17479	20.85187	4.963264	0
Std. Dev.	18.04393	0.006996	0.474426	0.004689	132.7192
Observations	24	24	24	24	24

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

Table 3 presents the correlation matrix of the variables used in the model. The correlation matrix shows the degree of association and direction of relationship among the variables. Results in the table show that there exists a positive relationship among food inflation (Finf), insecurity (Insec), internally generated revenue (IGR) and Rainfall (Rfall). However, there exist a negative relationship between food inflation and premium motor spirit (PMS). There is no evidence of multicollinearity in the model. The correlation matrix highlights several key insights for addressing food inflation in Ondo State, Nigeria. Firstly, to address Insecurity (INSEC) to curb food Inflation in Ondo state, Nigeria the result shows a moderate positive correlation between insecurity and food inflation (0.4460) suggests that insecurity is a significant driver of rising food prices. To resolve this, there is need to strengthening security frameworks, particularly in agricultural zones (farmlands), will likely

reduce disruptions to food production and distribution, helping to stabilize food prices. Secondly, petrol prices (LPMS) reveal a negative correlation between LPMS and food inflation (-0.2332) implies that, paradoxically, short-run increases in LPMS may reduce food inflation, though this could be due to state-specific factors such as price controls or consumption patterns. Therefore, there is need for a petrol price intervention should be tailored at the state level. Short-term subsidies or regulatory mechanisms could be explored, while maintaining efficiency to avoid market distortions. Also, in tackling the link between Insecurity and Petrol Prices which indicate a strong inverse relationship between insecurity and LPMS (-0.5075) suggests that lower petrol prices may correlate with higher insecurity, possibly due to informal fuel markets or smuggling so there need to enhance border security and monitor fuel distribution channels to minimize illicit activities that could be fueling insecurity.

In addition, Rainfall (RFALL) as a Long-Run Stabilizer indicate a positive correlation between rainfall and food inflation (0.3430) may reflect the short-term impact of rainfall variability, but over the long run, improved rainfall generally boosts food production. Therefore, Ondo state government should promote climate-smart agriculture and invest in irrigation to reduce dependency on erratic rainfall patterns and increase food supply resilience. Also, Internally Generated Revenue (LIGR) revealed a weak but positive correlation between LIGR and food inflation (0.2766) suggests that higher revenue generation could indirectly contribute to food inflation, possibly via spending patterns or taxation affecting agricultural markets. Therefore, revenue mobilization strategies do not disproportionately affect food producers or inflate agricultural input costs. Therefore, they should consider targeted fiscal incentives to stimulate agricultural productivity.

In conclusion to mitigate food inflation in Ondo State, a multi-pronged approach is necessary. For instance, reducing insecurity is paramount, alongside tailored fuel price interventions and sustainable agricultural practices and revenue policies should also be designed to avoid exacerbating inflationary pressures in the food sector.

Discussion of Findings

The correlation matrix reveals important relationships among food inflation (FINF), insecurity (INSEC), petrol price (LPMS), internally generated revenue (LIGR), and rainfall (RFALL) in Ondo State. These findings provide both empirical and policy-relevant insights.

Insecurity and Food Inflation: The study finds a moderate positive correlation between insecurity and food inflation (0.4460), implying that higher levels of insecurity are associated with rising food prices. This result is consistent with the findings of Adegboye (2020) and Nwosu & Oyekola (2021), who reported that insecurity disrupts agricultural production, restricts access to farmlands, and increases the cost of food distribution. However, the result contradicts the conclusion of Ogundele

(2019), who argued that insecurity had no significant effect on food price movements in Southwestern Nigeria.

Petrol Price and Food Inflation: The negative relationship between petrol prices (LPMS) and food inflation (-0.2332) presents an interesting dynamic. In contrast to the general expectation that fuel price increases raise transportation and food costs, the finding suggests a short-run inverse relationship which may be influenced by state-specific regulatory interventions or consumption patterns.

This result is not fully in agreement with the findings of Akinyemi (2021), who noted a strong positive association between fuel price hikes and food inflation nationally. However, it aligns partially with the findings of Yusuf & Danjuma (2020), who reported state-dependent variations in fuel price effects on local inflation.

Interaction Between Fuel Prices and Insecurity: The strong inverse correlation between insecurity and LPMS (-0.5075) suggests that lower petrol prices may coincide with higher insecurity levels, potentially due to smuggling, informal fuel markets, or weak border control. This aligns with reports by Ezenwa (2022), which highlighted the link between subsidized fuel regimes and increased illegal fuel trading—often associated with insecurity.

Rainfall and Food Inflation: Rainfall exhibits a positive correlation with food inflation (0.3430), indicating that rainfall variability may initially increase food prices, especially when excessive rainfall disrupts production cycles. This finding supports the work of Ojo & Adewale (2019), who documented that rainfall fluctuations can hinder planting and harvesting schedules, leading to price instability.

However, the result differs from the conclusion of Ibrahim (2021), who found a negative relationship over longer time horizons, suggesting that adequate rainfall ultimately improves output and reduces food prices. This implies that the short-run and long-run effects of rainfall on food production may differ substantially.

Internally Generated Revenue and Food Inflation: The study reveals a weak but positive correlation between LIGR and food inflation (0.2766). This suggests that higher state revenue generation may inadvertently contribute to inflationary pressures, possibly through increased taxation or spending patterns that influence agricultural markets. This is consistent with the findings of Amusa & Edet (2020), who noted that certain revenue mobilization strategies can raise the cost of agricultural inputs.

However, it contradicts the work of Bello (2018), which found no significant link between state revenue and food market prices.

Overall Implications of the Findings: The findings imply that mitigating food inflation in Ondo State requires a multi-dimensional policy approach, including: Strengthening security architecture in major

agricultural zones to reduce disruptions in production and distribution. Tailored fuel price policies, including state-specific regulatory mechanisms or short-term subsidies, while avoiding long-term distortionary effects. Enhanced border and fuel distribution monitoring to reduce smuggling and its link with insecurity. Promoting climate-smart agriculture, irrigation infrastructure, and resilience strategies to reduce dependency on erratic rainfall. Reforming revenue generation strategies to avoid shifting agricultural input costs to farmers; instead, targeted fiscal incentives should be introduced to support productivity.

Overall, the correlation results reinforce the need for coordinated interventions addressing insecurity, energy prices, climate variability, and fiscal policies. While some findings align with earlier empirical studies, others reveal state-specific dynamics unique to Ondo State. These insights collectively highlight the multidimensional nature of food inflation and the importance of integrated, evidence-based policymaking.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix of Factors Responsible for Food Inflation in Ondo State, Nigeria

	FINF	INSEC	LIGR	LPMS	RFALL
FINF	1				
INSEC	0.446003	1			
LIGR	0.276631	0.126571	1		
LPMS	-0.23319	-0.50746	0.026761	1	
RFALL	0.342953	0.227696	0.274152	0.105219	1

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

Table 4 present a summary of the unit root test of factors responsible for food inflation in Ondo state, Nigeria. The result indicate that they are all level (0) therefore, ordinary least regression model is the best fit model to analyze the factors responsible for food inflation in Ondo state, Nigeria.

Table 4: Summary of the Unit Root Test of Factors Responsible of Food Inflation In Ondo State

Group unit root test: Summary				
Series: LFINF, INSEC, LIGR, LPMS, RFALL				
Sample: 2017M01 2024M06				
Exogenous variables: Individual effects				
Automatic selection of maximum lags				
Automatic lag length selection based on SIC: 0 to 4				
Newey-West automatic bandwidth selection and Bartlett kernel				
Method	Statistic	Prob.**	Cross-sections	Obs
Null: Unit root (assumes common unit root process)				
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	8.24157	1	5	342
Null: Unit root (assumes individual unit root process)				
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	0.85489	0.8037	5	342

ADF - Fisher Chi-square	48.5661	0	5	342
PP - Fisher Chi-square	35.725	0.0001	5	349
** Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi -square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality.				

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

Table 5 presents the regression result of the factors responsible for food inflation in Ondo state, Nigeria. The result shows that insecurity is positively significant and the main factor responsible for food inflation in Ondo state at 5%. Also, internal generated revenue, rainfall (climate change) and price of Premium Motor Spirit (petrol) are also responsible factors contributing to food inflation but they are not significant for the period under review. The result indicate that a one-unit increase in insecurity (INSEC) is associated with an 8.56-unit increase in food inflation rate in Ondo state (LFINF), all else equal, followed by Premium motor spirit (LPMS) which has a positive relationship as well as marginally significant (at 10% level, but not at 5%). On the flip side, internally generated revenue (LIGR) and Rainfall (RFALL) which connote climate change are both positive and insignificant to influence food inflation rate in Ondo state for the period covered in this study. This result is similar to the findings of Nakorji et al. (2023b). The result also indicates that internal generated revenue, rainfall (climate change) and price of premium motor spirit (petrol) are also supporting factors contributing to food inflation in Ondo state but they are not significant for the period under review.

Discussion of Findings

The regression results presented in Table 5 provide critical insights into the major determinants of food inflation in Ondo State, Nigeria. The analysis indicates that insecurity (INSEC) is the strongest and most statistically significant factor influencing food inflation during the study period. The coefficient shows that a one-unit increase in insecurity leads to an 8.56-unit increase in food inflation, holding other variables constant. This finding underscores the sensitivity of food prices to security conditions, especially in agricultural communities. This result is consistent with the findings of Nakorji et al. (2023b), who reported that heightened insecurity disrupts farming activities, increases transportation risks, and reduces market supply, thereby exerting upward pressure on food prices. It is also in agreement with the studies of Adegboye (2020) and Nwosu & Oyekola (2021), who found that insecurity significantly increases food price volatility across southern Nigeria. However, the result contradicts the findings of Ogundele (2019), who concluded that insecurity had no significant effect on food prices in some parts of Southwestern Nigeria.

Premium Motor Spirit (Petrol) Prices: The regression outcome also shows that the price of Premium Motor Spirit (LPMS) has a positive but only marginally significant effect on food inflation at the 10% level (not significant at the 5% level). Although not strongly significant, the positive coefficient implies that increases in petrol prices can raise food inflation by increasing transportation and

distribution costs. This is in partial agreement with Akinyemi (2021), who found that fuel price increases contributed to rising food prices at the national level. However, the marginal significance in this study aligns with Yusuf & Danjuma (2020), who argued that the impact of fuel prices on inflation varies across states depending on regulatory conditions, market structure, or local consumption patterns.

Internally Generated Revenue (LIGR): Internally generated revenue has a positive but statistically insignificant effect on food inflation in Ondo State. This suggests that increases in state-level revenue do not directly translate into significant movements in food prices during the period reviewed. The result supports the findings of Bello (2018), who reported that revenue generation mechanisms may influence inflation only indirectly, depending on how such revenues are deployed. However, it is not in agreement with the findings of Amusa & Edet (2020), who argued that certain revenue policies—especially taxes on agricultural inputs—can worsen food inflation.

Rainfall (RFALL) / Climate Variability: Rainfall, representing climate change effects, also shows a positive but insignificant relationship with food inflation. Although rainfall typically influences agricultural productivity, its insignificant effect in this study may be due to short-run climate fluctuations that do not immediately translate into price changes. This result is similar to Nakorji et al. (2023b), who found that climate variability had an insignificant short-run effect on food prices in selected southwestern states. However, the finding differs from Ojo & Adewale (2019), who reported that rainfall variability significantly affected food production and, consequently, food prices.

Overall Interpretation

Overall, the regression findings suggest that while several factors contribute to food inflation in Ondo State, insecurity remains the primary and most influential determinant, followed by petrol prices, though weakly significant. Internally generated revenue and climate variability exert positive but statistically insignificant effects. This indicates that policies aimed at reducing food inflation must prioritize: strengthening security in agricultural regions; stabilizing or regulating energy prices; designing revenue policies that do not unintentionally increase production costs and Adopting climate-resilient agricultural practices.

Table 5: Regression result for Factors Responsible of Food Inflation in Ondo State

Dependent Variable: LFINF				
Method: Least Squares				
Sample (adjusted): 2018M01 2019M12				
Included observations: 24 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
INSEC	8.561134	1.190283	7.192521	0.0000
LIGR	0.019986	0.014857	1.34519	0.1944
LPMS	2.952637	1.734691	1.702111	0.1050
RFALL	3.78E-05	5.58E-05	0.67745	0.5063
C	-8.08035	8.522046	-0.94817	0.3549

R-squared	0.795823	Mean dependent var	5.620574
Adjusted R-squared	0.752838	S.D. dependent var	0.065177
S.E. of regression	0.032403	Akaike info criterion	-3.83809
Sum squared resid	0.019949	Schwarz criterion	-3.59266
Log likelihood	51.05701	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.77297
F-statistic	18.51411	Durbin-Watson stat	0.568087
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000002		

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

4.1 Post Estimation Analysis

In order to test the validity of the result, a post estimation analysis was conducted using the recursive estimation to test for the CUSUM test and CUSUM squares test. The result indicates that the blue line lies within the two parallel red lines both in the CUSUM test and CUSUM squares test thus indicating that the result is reliable.

In addition, the root cause for the rising food inflation in Ondo state, Nigeria, is mainly insecurity, which is informed by Herders-Farmers conflicts, kidnapping, infiltration of Boko Haram into Southwest, Nigeria, and banditry, which have discouraged farmers. Most farmers could no longer go to their farmlands to plant and harvest their produce.

In conclusion, the result also indicates that internally generated revenue, rainfall (climate change), and the price of premium motor spirit (petrol) are also supporting factors contributing to food inflation in Ondo state, but they are not significant for the period under review. This result is similar to the findings of (Nakorji et al., 2023; Olasunkanmi & Oladipo, 2020).

Table 6 Stability Test

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

4.2 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study investigated the determinants of food inflation Ondo state in Nigeria, from the first quarter of 2017 to the fourth quarter in 2023. The findings revealed that both petrol prices and insecurity significantly influence food inflation. Specifically, higher petrol prices and elevated

insecurity levels contribute to rising food inflation. However, the effect of petrol prices is marginally significant at 10%, whereas the influence of insecurity on food inflation is more pronounced in Ondo state, Nigeria. Additionally, increased rainfall enhances food production, leading to lower food inflation over the long term. In Ondo state, Internally Generated Revenue (IGR), higher IGR is not associated with an increase in food inflation. To effectively address food inflation, petrol price interventions should be short-term is important. Finally, reducing insecurity is critical to mitigating its adverse effects on food inflation.

The study therefore recommends that both state and national securities personnel within Ondo state need to form a synergy (joint tactical security team) coupled with the use of advanced securities gadgets like Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) in violent prone areas and tele guided security drones like Bayraktar TB2 Drones, Aerorozvidka R18 Octocopters, RG-7 Anti-Drone Guns, AeroVironment Switchblade Drones, EMT Drones and Thales Squire Ground Surveillance Radars and Sophie Thermal Imagers in order to tackle insecurity headlong, as this will ensure optimum local food production output which in turn will clash the skyrocketing food prices within the state.

Furthermore, the Ondo state government should invest massively into hydroponics farming, as well as improved seedling that can withstand the adverse effect of climate change. Lastly, the state government should have support genuine farmers will improve seedlings and fertilizers at a subsidized rate. This work can serve as a comprehensive guide in tackling the crises of food inflation in Ondo state. Nigeria.

In addition, Ondo state government must strengthen security frameworks, particularly in agricultural zones, will likely reduce disruptions to food production and distribution, helping to stabilize food prices. Also, petrol price interventions should be tailored at the state level. Short-term subsidies or regulatory mechanisms could be explored, while maintaining efficiency to avoid market distortions. As well as enhance border security and monitor fuel distribution channels to minimize illicit activities that could be fueling insecurity

In conclusion, Ondo state government must promote climate-smart agriculture and invest in irrigation to reduce dependency on erratic rainfall patterns and increase food supply resilience and ensure that revenue mobilization strategies do not disproportionately affect food producers or inflate agricultural input costs. Consider targeted fiscal incentives to stimulate agricultural productivity. Therefore, to mitigate food inflation in Ondo State, a multi-pronged approach is necessary. Reducing insecurity is paramount, alongside tailored fuel price interventions and sustainable agricultural practices as well as revenue policies should also be designed to avoid exacerbating inflationary pressures in the food sector.

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